

MSNetViews: Geographically Distributed Management of Enterprise Network Security Policy

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Policy Checker Rules:

Rule 1 (Dangling PE). Let PE be the policy elements, $PE \stackrel{def}{=} U \cup UA \cup OA \cup PC$. Where U is the set of users, UA is the set of user attributes, $OA \supseteq O$ is the set of object attributes (includes objects), and PC is the set of policy classes. If x is a policy element (i.e., $x \in (PE \setminus PC)$), then it must have a path of assignment relations towards at-least one policy class node $pc \in PC$, $x \rightsquigarrow pc$.

Rule 2 (Exclusive UA). A user attribute cannot belong to multiple policy classes. Let, UA is the set of user attributes and PC is the set of policy classes. If $x, y \in UA$ and $p, q \in PC$, then: $(x \rightsquigarrow p, y \rightsquigarrow q) \Rightarrow x \neq y$.

Rule 3 (Exclusive OA). A object attribute cannot belong to multiple policy classes. Let, OA is the set of object attributes, O is the set of objects and PC is the set of policy classes. If $x, y \in (OA \setminus O)$ and $p, q \in PC$, then: $(x \rightsquigarrow p, y \rightsquigarrow q) \Rightarrow x \neq y$.

Rule 4 ([Exclusive Associations]).] The association relation should be between nodes that belong to the same policy class. Let UA be the set of user attributes, OA the set of object attributes, O the set of objects, PC the set of policy classes, and \mathcal{R}_a the set of association relations, respectively. If $x \in UA$, $y \in (OA \setminus O)$ and $p, q \in PC$, then: $(x \rightsquigarrow p, y \rightsquigarrow q) \Rightarrow (x, ars, y) \notin \mathcal{R}_a$.

Rule 5 (Exclusive Prohibitions). The prohibition relation should be between nodes that belong to the same policy class. Let UA be the set of user attributes, OA the set of object attributes, O the set of objects, PC the set of policy classes, and \mathcal{R}_p the set of prohibition relations, respectively. If $x \in UA$, $y \in (OA \setminus O)$ and $p, q \in PC$, then: $(x \rightsquigarrow p, y \rightsquigarrow q) \Rightarrow (x, ars, y) \notin \mathcal{R}_p$.

The consolidated list of Policy Machine checks are as follows:

- All nodes need to be unique.
- Node type can be only $\langle OA, UA, U, O, PC, OS \rangle$.
- All node should have a parent or all node other than PC should be assigned to some node.
- Node declaration need at least three parameter. Node can not have a null or empty name, type and property.
- Assignment relation need child node and parent node only.
- Node with type PC can not be assigned to any thing.
- Node with type OA can only be assigned to node with type PC and OA .
- Node with type O can only be assigned to node with type OA .
- Node with type UA can only be assigned to node with type PC and UA .
- Node with type U can only be assigned to node with type UA .
- There can not multiple assignments between a pair of nodes.

- Association relation need at least three parameter.
- Association relation from UA to $\{UA, OA\}$ are only allowed.
- If there is already an association between two nodes, the current operation set (swap, not add) will be updated with new one.
- Prohibition can not be null, name can not be null, subject can not be null.
- There is checks provided for necessary fields on Obligation structure in general, event pattern, actions and functions.

Figure 1: Example of NGAC Policy Structure

Table 1: Parameters for Performance Overhead

Parameter	Value
Total flows in MiniStanford Topology	1k
Total flows in Cisco Topology	32
Traffic pattern for experiments with 2 sites	site 1 \rightarrow site 2
Wait between consecutive connections	100 ms
Same city latency (DC \leftrightarrow DC)	1 ms
Same region latency (DC \leftrightarrow NY)	11.2 ms
Global latency (DC \leftrightarrow CP)	105 ms

Table 2: NIST Network Requirements to Support ZTA

No.	Requirement	MSNet-Views
1.	Enterprise assets have basic network connectivity	Yes
2.	Enterprise can observe all network traffic	Yes
3a.	The enterprise must be able to distinguish between what assets are owned or managed by the enterprise	Yes
3b.	The enterprise must be able to distinguish between the devices' security postures	No
4.	Enterprise resources should not be reachable without accessing a PEP	Yes
5.	The data plane and control plane are logically separate	Yes
6.	Enterprise assets can reach the PEP component	Yes
7.	The PEP is the only component that accesses the policy administrator as part of a business flow	Yes
8.	Remote enterprise assets should be able to access enterprise resources without needing to traverse enterprise network infrastructure first	out-of-scope
9.	The infrastructure used to support the ZTA access decision process should be made scalable to account for changes in process load	Yes
10.	Enterprise assets may not be able to reach certain PEPs due to policy or observable factors	Yes

Algorithm 1 Create Local Policy For Site S_x

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1: procedure CREATELOCALPOLICY( $\mathcal{P}, O_x$ )
2:    $E = \text{GETRELEVANTELEMENTS}(\mathcal{P}, O_x)$ 
3:    $\mathcal{R} = \text{GETRELEVANTRELATIONS}(\mathcal{P}, E)$ 
4:   return  $\mathcal{P}_x = E \cup \mathcal{R}$ 
5: procedure GETRELEVANTELEMENTS( $\mathcal{P}, O_x$ )
6:    $OA_x = O_x, U_x = \emptyset, UA_x = \emptyset, \mathcal{R}_{a,x} = \emptyset, \mathcal{R}_{p,x} = \emptyset$ 
7:   for each  $o \in O_x$ 
8:      $OA'_x = \text{getAssignedOAs}(\mathcal{P}, o)$ 
9:      $\mathcal{R}_{a,x} = \mathcal{R}_{a,x} \cup \text{getAssociations}(\mathcal{P}, OA'_x)$ 
10:     $OA_x = OA_x \cup OA'_x$ 
11:   for each  $(ua, \_, oa) \in \{\mathcal{R}_{a,x} \cup \mathcal{R}_{p,x}\}$ 
12:      $UA_p = \text{getParentUAs}(\mathcal{P}, ua)$ 
13:      $UA_c = \text{getChildUAs}(\mathcal{P}, ua)$ 
14:      $U_x = U_x \cup \text{getUsers}(\mathcal{P}, ua)$ 
15:      $UA_x = UA_x \cup ua \cup UA_p \cup UA_c$ 
16:   return  $E = U_x \cup UA_x \cup OA_x \cup \text{getPCs}(\mathcal{P})$ 
17: procedure GETRELEVANTRELATIONS( $\mathcal{P}, E$ )
18:    $\mathcal{R}_x = \emptyset$ 
19:   for each  $e \in E$ 
20:     for each  $r \in \text{getAssignments}(\mathcal{P}, e)$ 
21:       if  $r.source \in E$  and  $r.target \in E$  then
22:          $\mathcal{R}_x = \mathcal{R}_x \cup r$ 
23:     for each  $r \in \text{getAssociations}(\mathcal{P}, e)$ 
24:       if  $r.source \in E$  and  $r.target \in E$  then
25:          $\mathcal{R}_x = \mathcal{R}_x \cup r$ 
26:     for each  $r \in \text{getProhibitions}(\mathcal{P}, e)$ 
27:       if  $r.subject \in E$  and  $r.container \in E$  then
28:          $\mathcal{R}_x = \mathcal{R}_x \cup r$ 
29:   return  $\mathcal{R}_x$ 

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